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**THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE EFFICIENCY OF COMPANIES:
SECTORAL AND SPATIAL ASPECTS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE
SOUTH-SIBERIAN REGION).
MOTIVATION & RESEARCH QUESTION**

The COVID-19 pandemic is now one of the most popular research topics in Russia and around the world. Almost all economic studies since 2020 include an analysis of changes associated with two aspects of the pandemic: morbidity and mortality from COVID-19, as well as restrictions associated with the pandemic. This is because COVID-19 in one way or another has affected every person in the world and absolutely all areas of life. Even if someone has never been sick with covid, they still faced lockdown, loss of work and decrease in income, rising prices for essential goods, closing their favorite cafe, etc.

Different industries have been affected differently by the pandemic. The global scientific community agrees on which business sectors have suffered the most. This is primarily tourism, trade, transport and other offline services. But at the same time, industries such as medicine and food delivery, on the contrary, "grew" due to the pandemic, also some industries such as public utilities, agriculture, extractive industry and others remained almost unchanged. And of course, this factor should be taken into account in the analysis. Western scientists, studying spatial dependencies, come to the conclusion that covid restrictions affect not only the territories where they are introduced, but also neighboring ones. This means that when analyzing the impact of COVID-19 on the economy, one must take into account that this impact is different depending on the industry and territory.

Currently, there are no COVID-19 studies in Russia that would consider both the sectoral and spatial aspects. Foreign works show that the study of the influence of these two factors in combination gives good results. The purpose of our work is to assess the direct (on the company itself) and indirect (on neighboring) impact of pandemic restrictions on the financial performance of Russian companies of various industry groups.

Literature review

Let's look at world and Russian studies related to COVID-19 and analyzing the impact of the pandemic in an industry and spatial aspect.

M. Carvalho [Carvalho et al., 2022] examines the impact of the possibility of remote work on economic recovery after the acute phase of the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors build two models to explain the increase in unemployment

from February to April and its fall from April to December, where the units of observation are the counties of the southern US states. The explanatory variables are the weighted average teleworkability for each county (which is estimated for each industry and multiplied by the industry's share of the county's output), the unemployment rate in neighboring counties, and some control variables. The authors come to the conclusion that high teleworkability significantly accelerates the decline in unemployment in the post-crisis period, and unemployment in the nearest districts does not have a significant impact.

Let's look at Russian research. A. Zaytseva [Зайцева et al., 2020] note in their work that small and medium-sized businesses have suffered the most as a result of the pandemic. The authors analyzed the results of a survey of 1,500 entrepreneurs throughout Russia. 2% of entrepreneurs said that the COVID-19 pandemic had a positive impact on business, 10% said they did not significantly affect, and the remaining 85% of entrepreneurs believe that the pandemic affected business negatively. Respondents also named 9 industries that, in their opinion, suffered the most in 2020: catering (37%), tourism and recreation (34%), trade (26%), services (22%), entertainment (18%), transport and logistics (17%), sports (7%), industrial production (6%) and beauty industry (5%). The authors of the article also write that measures to combat the epidemic through isolation and quarantine lead to a decrease in the production capacity of enterprises and interruptions in the activities of not only the companies themselves, but also their counterparties. Supply chains are interrupted, resulting in reduced availability of raw materials and components. Thus, if a company has not fallen under direct restrictions, this does not mean that it will not suffer damage.

E. A. Коломак in her article [Коломак, 2020], based on Rosstat data, ranks industries with the largest drop in value added (May 2020 to May 2019). Most of all, paid services to the population "fell" (value added decreased by 39,5%), retail trade (-19,2%), mining (-13,5%), industrial production in general (-9,6%) and manufacturing industries (-7,2%). It can be seen that, although the method for assessing damage to the industry differs significantly from the previous article [Zaitseva et al., 2020], the list of the most affected industries is generally similar. To compare the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on different regions, the author assessed the growth/decline in the total output in the listed industries (as the most "sensitive"). On average, output in these industries fell by 25%, which is a significant indicator. The most affected regions are Sevastopol (-56%), the Republic of Chechnya (-54%), the Republic of Dagestan (-52%), Khabarovsk Territory (-49%), Primorsky Territory (-48%) and Krasnodar Territory (-43 %). The least affected are the Republic of Komi (-8%), the Khanty-Mansiysk Autonomous Okrug (-8%), the Republic of Adygea (-8%), the Novosibirsk Region (-6%), the Republic of Khakassia (+1%) and the Nenets Autonomous Okrug (+4%). It can be seen that the difference between the regions is huge, and among both the heavily affected and unaffected regions there are regions of different location, specialization and well-being. To find out the reasons why some regions are more

affected by COVID-19, while others are less, the author uses regression analysis. The author found that a high level of urbanization, the number of small businesses and mining reduces the negative impact of the pandemic and related restrictions, while a high level of gross regional product increases it. The author also comes to the conclusion that, despite state support and non-market restrictions for business, the COVID-19 pandemic has increased the economic divergence of Russian regions.

Natalia Zubarevich with colleagues [Макаренцева et al., 2020] consider changes in the labor market in Russian regions in spring-summer 2020. In Russia as a whole, the number of part-time workers increased from 1,3 million to 2,2 million in one quarter, and the share of part-time workers increased from 3,8% to 6,3% of the payroll (in growth was mainly due to industrial cities and large agglomerations with strict quarantine restrictions). The unemployment rate according to the methodology of the International Labor Organization increased slightly during the crisis (from 4,6% to 6,2% per quarter), in contrast to the registered unemployment rate (from 1% to 4,4% over the same period). This discrepancy is explained by the fact that unemployment benefits were increased, and people began to massively register with employment centers. Geographically, the largest increase in registered unemployment was observed in the agglomerations of the largest cities, where the service sector prevails, as well as in underdeveloped regions with a significant share of the shadow economy – many illegally employed were able to register for unemployment according to simplified rules. The real incomes of the population for the year decreased by 8% on average in Russia (with a wide spread across regions – from +4% to -17%). Thus, we see a significant impact of COVID-19 also on labor markets, and with great territorial heterogeneity.

Based on the review of the literature, it can be concluded that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the activities of companies is significant and, no less important, heterogeneous in terms of space and industry. However, there are no studies in Russia that would take into account not only interregional differences, but also spatial effects.

In our work, we plan to explore how the influence of industry affiliation and spatial effects on company performance changes from 2019 to 2020 (before and during the pandemic, respectively).

Methodology

We used information about 8226 companies in the South-Siberian region (Novosibirsk oblast, Kemerovo oblast, Omsk and Tomsk oblasts, Altay kray and south of Krasnoyarsk kray) from the "Spark-Interfax" database.

We built two Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) with spatial lag – for 2019 and 2020 years separately [Балаш, 2011]. Geographically Weighted Regression is the usual regression, except that the coefficients of this regression

depend on the location of the object in space (in practice, for each point, a separate regression is estimated for a certain radius around it):

$$Y = \beta(u, v) * X + \gamma(u, v) * WY + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where Y – dependent variable, X – independent variables, W – spatial weight matrix (reverse distance from firm i to firm j ($i \neq j$), if i and j belong to the same branch group, 0 otherwise), β and γ – coefficients, u and v – geographical coordinates, ε – random error.

The dependent variable is the sales margin (SM), the explanatory variables are dummy variables for various industry groups (in accordance with OKVED), the spatial lag of the SM, agglomeration effect, and some control variables: the age of the company, its scale, capital intensity, share of borrowed funds in assets, and "regional" variable – unemployment rate in the region.

Since the inclusion of the spatial lag of the profitability of sales raises the problem of endogeneity (since the influence of neighboring enterprises is mutual), we used the Two Stages Least Square Procedure to evaluate the regression [Kelejian, 1997; Demidova, 2022].

Results and Discussion

The results of the regression evaluation showed that:

1) For companies under 5 years old in 2019, the return on sales was lower by an average of 1.8 percentage points, and in 2020 the age factor turned out to be insignificant;

2) Both before the crisis and during the crisis, the lowest return on sales was observed in medium-sized companies (revenue from 800 million to 2 billion per year): by about 5 p.p. lower than for microbusiness, and by 4-5 p.p. less than for small and large (perhaps this is due to the fact that neither the effect of a low base nor the effect of scale works for a medium business);

3) In 2020, profitability decreased for companies in the information and communication industry (-5 p.p. compared to agriculture) and real estate operations (-6 p.p., respectively);

4) In 2019, in the healthcare and social services industry, profitability was higher by an average of 11 percentage points, during the crisis this advantage disappeared (possibly due to the fact that people began to do fewer elective procedures in private clinics);

5) For the culture and sports industry in 2019, profitability was 12 p.p. lower than for agriculture, in 2020 the difference became insignificant;

6) In 2019, leverage and capital intensity did not affect return on sales, while in 2020 their impact was significant and negative (this can be explained by the fact that companies with a high leverage are more at risk, and during the COVID-19 crisis those risks have materialised).

7) The agglomeration effect (the number of companies in their industry group within a radius of 20 km) was significant and positive both in 2019 and

2020: +1 company in their industry gives an average of + 0.001 p.p. to profitability of sales;

8) The spatial lag was significant and positive in 2019 and insignificant in 2020: an increase in the weighted average profitability in neighboring companies in the same industry by 1 p.p. gave + 0.26 p.p. in 2019 (this can be explained by the fact that during the crisis, offline interaction has decreased, and the influence of neighbors has become less).

What problems remain to be solved? First, the sample (South Siberian companies) is quite homogeneous, and in the future we plan to expand the sample to all regions of Russia. Secondly, there is no such analysis of regional differences in the work yet, and we plan to add either dummy variables for each region, or more regional variables (average salary, share of unprofitable enterprises, crime, etc.). Thirdly, there are as yet no variables responsible for the severity of COVID-19 restrictions in a particular locality, although they can significantly affect the efficiency of companies.

References:

1. Carvalho M., Hagerman A. D., Whitacre B. (2022) Telework and COVID-19 resiliency in the southeastern united states, *Journal of Regional Analysis & Policy* 52:1, 19–34
2. Demidova O. A., Kuletskaja L. E., Podkolzina E. A. (2022) Spatial modelling of voting preferences: The “Mystery” of the Republic of Tatarstan, *Applied econometrics*, 67, 74-96
3. Kelejian H.H., Prucha I.R. (1997) A Generalized Spatial Two Stage Least Squares Procedure for Estimating a Spatial Autoregressive Model with Autoregressive Disturbances, *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 17:1, 99–121
4. Балаш В. А., Балаш О. С., Харламов А.В. (2011) Эконометрический анализ геокодированных данных о ценах на жилую недвижимость, *Прикладная эконометрика*, 22:2, 62-77
5. Зайцева А. О., Кокина А. Н., Печерица Е. В. (2020) Анализ влияния пандемии COVID-19 на малый и средний бизнес России, *Здоровье – основа человеческого потенциала: проблемы и пути их решения* 25:3, 1459-1465
6. Коломак Е. А. (2020) Экономические последствия COVID-19 для регионов России, *ЭКО* 558:12, 143-153
7. Макаренцева А. О., Мкртчян Н. В., Зубаревич Н. В. (2020) Демографическая ситуация и социально-экономическое развитие регионов России в первой половине 2020 Г., *Экономическое развитие России* 27:10, 73-88